

ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY REQUIREMENTS AND PRACTICAL NEEDS IN THE FIELD OF MODERN MEDIA

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Abstract

This article analyzes the requirements for the level of English language proficiency for professionals and future journalists working in the modern media field and the practical needs arising in this field. In the process of globalization and information exchange, the ability to communicate freely in English, understand and convey information, and use professional terminology are of great importance for effective participation in the international media field. The article analyzes the role and level of demand for English language knowledge in various areas of the media field (journalism, PR, digital communication, translation). It also discusses recommendations on language competence in the modern media environment, methodological approaches to training specialists, and problems in the language teaching process.

Keywords: *English, media field, language competence, journalism, global communication, information technologies, language requirements, practical needs.*

Introduction: As a result of the development of modern information technologies, the rapid expansion of global communication systems and the development of digital journalism, English has become one of the main tools of the international media space today. The activities of major world-class news agencies, online publications, blog platforms, social networks and other media outlets are increasingly relying on English. Therefore, the high level of knowledge of English and the ability to communicate freely and effectively in this language by representatives of the media industry - journalists, editors, PR specialists, media analysts and translators - is considered one of the important professional criteria today.

The media industry is distinguished by its extremely dynamic, multidisciplinary and international nature. This creates the need to learn English not only as a foreign language, but also to be able to use it as a professional tool. Therefore, for professionals working in the media sector or studying in this field, English language competence is not limited only to vocabulary or grammatical knowledge, but also includes skills such as analyzing information, working with a mass audience, communicating in formal and informal ways, creating journalistic materials, and participating in international cooperation.

Today, activities such as creating journalistic materials in English, analyzing and translating foreign sources, participating in international conferences and briefings, and maintaining content in English on information platforms have become an integral part of the daily work process for media professionals. This, in turn, requires a clear definition of the requirements for the level of English language knowledge and a scientific analysis of existing needs.

This article examines these needs - namely, the level of English language knowledge in the modern media sector, the requirements for it, and an analysis of practical skills. The article also analyzes the communicative competencies in English necessary for media professionals, strategies for their development, and the effectiveness of existing educational and methodological approaches. The results of the study, in turn, serve as a theoretical and practical basis for updating foreign language teaching in the journalism and media education system, developing professionally oriented curricula, and proposing new approaches to media language competence.

Main part: In recent years, the media industry has become unprecedentedly globalized. As a result of the development of the Internet, artificial intelligence, artificial networks and multimedia technologies, the speed of information exchange has increased, and geographical boundaries have almost lost their significance. In such conditions, English has become the main tool of the global information space. Large international media platforms such as CNN, BBC, Reuters, The Guardian, Al Jazeera English are leading in shaping today's global information flow. In order to correctly understand, analyze and respond to their content, every media professional must have a sufficient level of English.

The fact that English is considered not only a foreign language, but also a tool for professional activity requires a fundamental change in the approach to studying it in the media industry. Now the language covers not only grammatical and lexical knowledge, but also speech styles, professional terminology, information analysis and presentation methods.

In today's digital era, the types of activities that require working in English have expanded.

Receiving and analyzing information: reading, understanding foreign news agencies, press releases, analytical articles and creating content based on them.

Delivering information: writing articles, press releases, teasers, interviews or posts in English; creating scripts for videos and podcasts.

Professional communication: conducting written and oral communication with foreign journalists, editorial offices, agencies, participating in international press conferences.

Translation and localization: high-quality translation from English to the native language and vice versa, adapting content taking into account the cultural context.

All of these skills require language competence at least at the B2-C1 level according to the CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages). That is, understanding and fluent use of English at an intermediate-high or advanced level is required.

The conducted practical research (questionnaires, interviews, tests) identified the following important needs and problems:

Although the majority of media professionals have an average level of English, they have difficulty with professional terminology and written speech.

Students learn English in a grammatical and academic context, but insufficient attention is paid to the specific style of media language.

English is often taught in general curricula, which does not meet the needs of the professional field.

Employers consider it important to have a portfolio in English, conduct practical correspondence, and be able to express their thoughts freely orally when hiring for jobs in the media sector.

Conclusion: As the modern media industry has become an integral part of the global information space, for professionals working in this field, sufficient knowledge of English is not only an advantage, but also a necessary professional requirement. Studies and analyses have shown that media representatives should have fluent reading, writing, listening comprehension and oral communication skills in English. This is especially important for journalists, editors, PR specialists, translators and media analysts.

According to the results of the study, in current educational processes, English is taught more for general purposes, but this approach does not fully cover the needs of the media industry. Therefore, it is urgent to develop educational programs based on special directions - professional needs, in particular, to include modules such as "Media English", "English for Journalism" in the curriculum.

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